

Empowerment of Msmes by Optimizing Marketing of Local Products in Muntuk Hamlet with Digital Marketing

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ABSTRACT

Muntuk Village is located in Dlingo District, Bantul Regency, Special Region of Yogyakarta. Muntuk Village is located in the east of Bantul City. Meanwhile, most of the residents of Dusun Muntuk work as day laborers, farmers, gardeners, wood and bamboo craftsmen. The majority of the population of Muntuk Hamlet work as wood craftsmen (furniture) and bamboo (woven) craftsmen. However, there are also those who work as farmers and traders, but that is only a side job because their main job is wood and bamboo craftsman. The people of Muntuk Village, the majority of whom work as wood craftsmen (meuble) and bamboo craftsmen (anyman) have problems, namely the lack of knowledge and understanding and access to promote these handicraft products using social media, resulting in less than optimal sales and the community's income does not develop. To overcome this, the local government can increase the entrepreneurial potential of the Muntuk Village community through micro and cultural policies, providing facilities, providing education and knowledge to the community in collaboration with surrounding campuses. The government also needs to pay attention to entrepreneurs so that they can use social media as a marketing medium so that they can expand the market more broadly which will ultimately help the economy of the Muntuk Village community.

KEYWORDS

Muntu Hamlet;
bamboo craftsmen;
social media;
Digital Marketing;
MSMES

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1. Introduction

Muntuk Village is located in Dlingo District, Bantul Regency, Special Region of Yogyakarta. Muntuk Village is located in the east of Bantul City. Meanwhile, most of the residents of Dusun Muntuk work as day laborers, farmers, gardeners, wood and bamboo craftsmen. The majority of the population of Dusun Muntuk work as wood craftsmen (furniture) and bamboo (woven) craftsmen. However, there are also those who work as farmers and traders, but that is only a side job because their main job is wood and bamboo craftsman. The people of Muntuk Village, the majority of whom work as wood craftsmen (meuble) and bamboo craftsmen (anyman) have problems, namely the lack of knowledge and understanding and access to promote these handicraft products using social media, resulting in less than optimal sales and the community's income does not develop.

Digital marketing is an effort made to promote goods or services through digital media that can reach the wider community. Marketing has been studied by previous researchers to become a reference for this community empowerment. Sustainability and retail marketing: The company, product, and store perspective researched by Elg [1]. Do health insurance companies use target marketing as a tool for risk selection? Evidence from the Netherlands was investigated by Stolper [2]. Technology-based student business incubation: The importance of networking and team recruitment is researched by Haneberg [3].

Diaspora, agencies and companies in the context of settlements and the homeland: Politicized entrepreneurship in the Kurdish diaspora is researched by Syrett [4]. A Post-Marketing Surveillance Study to Evaluate the Safety Profile of Alvotere® (Docetaxel) in Iranian Patients Diagnosed with Various Types of Cancer Receiving Chemotherapy was investigated by [5]. Escape from the Red Queen: Health as a corporate food marketing strategy was researched by Cuevas [6]. Opportunities and barriers to innovation and entrepreneurship in the development of orphan drugs were investigated by Belousova [7]. How is energy important? Rural electricity, entrepreneurship, and community development in Kenya were investigated by Vernet [8]. Past, present, and future customer engagement was investigated by [9]. Establishing B2B digital marketing in artificial intelligence-based CRM: An overview and direction for future research researched by Saura [10]. The formal institutional context of informal entrepreneurship: A cross-country configuration-based perspective was investigated by Ault [11]. Incorporated entrepreneurship in Norway: Tendency and resilience investigated by Kolvereid [12]. Using a 'lens' to research business markets, relationships and networks: Tensions, challenges, and possibilities researched by Ojansivu [13]. Researching artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in marketing through a global lens: Current trends and future research opportunities are examined by Kopalle [14]. The impact of value and future orientation on intention formation in sustainable entrepreneurship was investigated by Thelken [15]. Yin and Yang entrepreneurship: Gender differences in the importance of communal and agency characteristics for subjective well-being and entrepreneur performance were investigated by Hmieleski [16]. TikTok's effect on destination development: Famous overnight, now what? investigated by Wenge [17]. Blockchain Technology Applications in Marketing—A systematic review of marketing technology companies was researched by Stallone [18]. Digital sustainable entrepreneurship: The business model perspective in embedding digital technology for social and environmental value creation was researched by Gregori [19]. Smart cities and entrepreneurship: An agenda for future research researched by Kummitha [20].

“We Go Together”: Understanding purchase intentions related to social goals of young adults was investigated by [21]. Adolescent exposure to cannabis marketing following the legalization of recreational marijuana in Canada: A pilot study using an ecological momentary assessment was investigated by Noël [22]. The impact of promoting sustainable entrepreneurship in a generic business plan competition was investigated by Fichter [23]. Digital entrepreneurship and the field conditions for institutional change—Investigating the role of enabling cities is investigated by Geissinger [24]. The choice of mode of exchange of small exporting firms in international marketing channels for perishable products: A contingency approach was investigated by Nyu [25]. Examining the effect of commercialization and postharvest losses on the choice of marketing outlets among poultry farmers was investigated by Bannor [26]. How do cultural values influence the nation's entrepreneurial behavior? The behavioral reasoning approach was investigated by Calza [27]. Towards a Taxonomy of Entrepreneurial Education Research Literature: Mapping and Bibliometric Visualization investigated by [28]. Negative producer price differentials in Federal Milk Marketing Orders: Explanation, implications, and policy options researched by Bozic [29]. Multilevel trust in the international marketing of health services: A five-country comparative study researched by Fregidou-Malama [30]. Entrepreneurship and sustainable bioeconomic transformation were investigated by Kuckertz [31]. Local entrepreneurship and social services in Romania. Territorial analysis was investigated by Chivu [32]. Post-Marketing Control of Generic Oxaliplatin (Alvoxal®) in Iranian Patients with Cancer was studied by Shahi [33]. Spillover effects of direct competition between marketing cooperatives and private intermediaries: Evidence from the Thai rice value chain was examined by Kumse [34]. Engineering entrepreneurship problems in Africa: An example of design optimization in solar thermal engineering was investigated by Kanyarusoke [35].

Research model for social business financing: theory and practice researched by Akbulaev [36]. The marketing of sugar-sweetened beverages to youth through US universities includes contractual rights researched by Marx [37]. Social marketing and behavior change in systems settings were investigated by Domegan [38]. Effectiveness of entrepreneurship training, government entrepreneurship support and venturing of TVET students into IT-related entrepreneurship – Indirect pathway effect analysis investigated by Salisu [39]. Data survey on the antecedents of entrepreneurial intention in Indonesia was investigated by Wijaya [40]. Social media, which is supported by the current development of science and technology, has the potential to support the success of a business in a fast and easy way. Creativity is also very necessary in this case so that consumers are also interested in buying the products offered. However,

the problem is that not all local communities, especially the Muntuk Village community, can use social media as a forum to promote these goods or services, so it is necessary to provide understanding to the Muntuk Village community so that they can use social media according to their functions and can also help the Village community. Poor in the field of economy.

To overcome this, the local government can increase the entrepreneurial potential of the Muntuk Village community through micro and cultural policies, providing facilities, providing education and knowledge to the community in collaboration with surrounding campuses. The government also needs to pay attention to entrepreneurs so that they can use social media as a marketing medium so that they can expand the market more broadly which will ultimately help the economy of the Muntuk Village community.

2. Method

The activity plans in order to implement the solutions offered, in detail are:

- Making product photos that will be accompanied directly August 19, 2020
- Cataloging is done by selecting several photos that have been taken and then edited and then entered into the website belonging to Dusun Muntuk, 19 August 2020
- Website creation that will be accompanied directly 19-22 August 2020
- Directly assisted online marketing socialization August 23, 2020
- Personally assisted IT training 23 August 2020

3. Results and Discussion

The service workers make observations of furniture and bamboo craftsmen about how to market their products as shown in Figure 1. The picture shows that two community empowerment students are making observations to the owners of MSMEs.

Fig. 1. Observation of Furniture and Bamboo Craftsmen

The servants taking product photos are shown in Figure 2. The image shows a person doing a catalog where in the catalog creation process is done by selecting several photos that have been taken from the bamboo and furniture craftsmen of Dukuh Muntuk, the process of making a catalog by editing photos and inserting them into the website owned Muntu Village.

Fig. 2. Product Photo Process

The servants assisting in the website creation process are shown in Figure 3. The figure shows that the website creation process is carried out by the servants and is then followed up by carrying out marketing socialization as well as website introduction and website management training.

Fig. 3. Website Development Socialization and Training

This is a display from the website for bamboo handicrafts and furniture in Dukuh Muntuk, shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Website Display

When the charm website is opened, an article will immediately appear containing a description of the type of wood used along with an explanation, which can be seen in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Display of the Website's First Article

Not only articles but on the charm website there are several views that are provided which consist of a website gallery display and a website operating view. It can be seen in Figures 6 and 7.

Fig. 6. Website Gallery Display

Fig. 7. Views for Operating the Website

4. Conclusion

In this website creation program, the devotees make various efforts to increase public awareness of the importance of entrepreneurship and how to develop it. The initial process for the devotees was to interview furniture and bamboo craftsmen in Dukuh Muntuk about how to do marketing. Furthermore, the servants took content for the contents of the website which would be submitted to the residents of Dukuh Muntuk. Then the servants carried out online marketing socialization by introducing the importance of branding and social media as a medium of online marketing to the community, especially entrepreneurs and youth of Dukuh Muntuk and introducing a website that would be handed over to Dukuh Muntuk residents. The last stage for the devotees is to conduct training in managing the website for the young people who will manage the website.

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